

INNOVATIVE WAYS TO ELIMINATE THE MIGRATION PROBLEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. There are approximately 281 million international migrants in the world today - 3.6% of the world's population. Such information is provided by the UN press service in connection with the beginning of the International Migration Week under the leadership of the UN. The aim of the initiative is to review the implementation of the Global Agreement on Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration.

Keywords. Migration, innovative ways, world economy, labor migration.

Introduction. During the integration and liberalization of the world economy in the first quarter of the last century, the importance of labor migration in the social and economic development of the country and the attention of the general public is increasing year by year. The problems of labor migration are especially important for Uzbekistan, which is rich in labor resources and one of the main participants of international labor migration. For this reason, the article describes the causes of labor migration in Uzbekistan, its characteristics, current situation and prospects in detail. There are deep-rooted reasons for the emergence and rapid development of labor migration in the country. The occurrence and escalation of these processes are associated with the independence of Uzbekistan and the transition from planned economy to free market relations. In the early

stages of independence, it was recognized that labor migration was one of the main means of protection against economic stress and social conflicts in the country. Until now, the state policy on foreign labor migration, which was hastily formed under the pressure of the acute situation in those times, does not meet the requirements of today's times. First of all, it does not correspond to the essence of the strategy of rapid development of the national economy of New Uzbekistan. During the more than 30 years since independence, the socio-economic situation in the country has changed dramatically, new opportunities have emerged to solve the problems of unemployment and employment, and the scope of results that can be achieved due to foreign labor migration has expanded. Based on the practical results of large-scale economic reforms implemented in the framework of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan, fundamental changes should be made in the country's labor migration policy. Ways to improve this policy have been developed and mechanisms for effective organization of labor migration in the republic have been proposed.

Economic reforms in developing countries, unemployment, poverty or, on the contrary, the movement of the population to developed countries as a result of the desire for a better life, cause the issue of migration to be discussed with great interest in the fields of philosophy, sociology, political science, psychology, and pedagogy. Regardless of the type of migration, it causes radical changes and profound changes in society, family, and human life. Today, this process, which is somewhat popular, has gained a solid name in science under the name of "population migration" (lat. migratio - migration). Population migration is the movement of people from one area to another, sometimes in large groups and over long distances. If a migrant is a person who temporarily or permanently moves to live in a new place, a migrant who enters the territory of the country of new residence is called an immigrant, and a migrant who leaves the territory of the country of residence is called an emigrant. Analysis of the literature showed

that migration can occur for 3 reasons: economic factors, natural disaster, despair. Also, "in addition to economic factors, there are other influences in the implementation of the migration process, among which environmental, psychological, and legal factors can be included." The psychological reasons that encourage labor migrants to change their place of residence are related to the desire for a comfortable marriage in terms of personal safety and satisfaction of psychological and other needs. It is important not only to earn a good income, but also to expand one's opportunities and strive for self-development. Some migrants intend to live in this place for a long time by marrying representatives living in this area for the purpose of marriage. This may be related to the desire to change one's life for the better.

According to the statistics of the United Nations, the world's population growth has increased. At different periods of human history, a large part of the world's population lives not in the country of birth, but in the countries to which they have migrated. According to data, the number of migrants reached 272 million in 2019 on an international scale. In 2000, this figure was 173 million. In a short time, this figure increased to 100 million. It is noteworthy that 48% of the total share of migrants are women, while 38 mln. Children are active participants in this process. Only 4.4 million migrants. 164 mln. of students who left for education. are cocktail migrants. 75% of migrants are people of working age (20-64 years old), who spend their physical and mental energy on the growing national economy. The share of migrants in the structure of the permanent population of the continents is 31% in Asia, 30% in Europe, 26% in North and South America, 10% in Africa, and 3% in Oceania.

Discussion. Vladimir Syurko, the head of the office of the UN High Commissioner for Refugees in Russia, said that the scale of migration in the world is expanding, "Today, the total number of immigrants is around 250 million people, most of them migrate voluntarily in search of work. "The scale of

migration is unbelievably large, it has never happened before, and these numbers continue to grow," he said.

Migration is the movement of people. Migration for work is the migration of the population to another region, state for the purpose of work and earning money.

We all know that most of the citizens of our country have experienced and continue to experience the difficult situation of working as a migrant. We can say that this is one of the most painful points of the nation. There are both negative and positive aspects of migration. We can find out the level of migration through statistics about our citizens who leave our country and work as migrants in another country.

If we look at the 5-year forecast in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2015, the immigration statistics of Uzbekistan amounted to 1,170,899.00, which decreased by 4.04% compared to 2010. In 2010, the immigration statistics of Uzbekistan amounted to 1,220,149.00, which decreased by 8.21% compared to 2005. Uzbekistan immigration statistics for 2005 amounted to 1,329,345.00, which decreased by 5.4% compared to 2000. In 2000, the immigration statistics of Uzbekistan amounted to 1,405,250.00, which decreased by 7.1% compared to 1995.

Statistics show that the current net migration rate for Uzbekistan in 2022 is -0.261 per 1000 population, which is a decrease of 1.14% compared to 2021. In 2021, the net migration rate for Uzbekistan was -0.264 per 1000 inhabitants, which decreased by 1.49% compared to 2020. In 2020, the net migration rate for Uzbekistan was -0.268 per 1000 inhabitants, which decreased by 1.11% compared to 2019. In 2019, the net migration rate for Uzbekistan was -0.271 per 1000 inhabitants, which decreased by 1.45% compared to 2018.

According to the data, we can see that the number of migrants from Uzbekistan is decreasing every year, but the differences in these numbers are very

small. That is, these indicators showing that citizens of our country live as migrants in other countries and are migrants in other countries are one of our most painful points. One of the good sides of migration is the improvement of people's knowledge and skills, that is, citizens who go to work abroad can learn new things that have not yet been used in our country and apply them in our country, which leads to development in its place.

Another good thing about migration is that it brings foreign currency into the country. Thanks to this, the republic can communicate with other countries, carry out trade, etc. But there are other ways to import foreign currency. For this, we must prepare our products in accordance with world requirements and sell them to other countries. In this case, we can see the currency exchange. First of all, in order to meet the demands of other countries, we should become a member of the World Trade Organization in order to produce goods that can meet their demands. What does this give us? Membership in the World Trade Organization will help increase competition and, as a result, increase our production and its quality.

What should be done to reduce migration and migration among Uzbeks? For this, first of all, we need to create more jobs in our country. How to create a job? And for this we need to expand more production and industry. In order to expand these, we need to attract more investors to our country. Only then will we have enough jobs. As we mentioned above, one of the benefits of migration is the influx of foreign currency. Currency is very important. Once we create jobs in our country, we will not only have employment for our people, but also foreign exchange will start flowing into us.

That is, after we release our domestically produced products to the foreign trade market, currency will automatically come to us and can be a solution to many problems. In terms of attracting investors to Uzbekistan, we can take as an example the international conference "International investment forum in

Tashkent", which was held in our country on 24-25-26, 2022. The main goal of this conference is to attract investors from all over the world to Uzbekistan. It is necessary to organize many such conferences, not just once.

In addition, most of the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan work as migrants to the Russian Federation. This situation has existed for a long time, that is, most of the migrants from the Republic of Uzbekistan work in Russia before and now. Current political events also have an impact on Uzbekistan. As a result of the fall of the ruble, the exchange rate entering Uzbekistan will also decrease significantly. The unemployment rate will also rise, and at the same time, the price level will also rise. The reason for this is the low inflow of foreign currencies such as the US dollar and Euro in our country and the increase in value of the soum. The price of imported products will also become more expensive, and this may have a negative impact on the standard of living of the population. It is in this case that the need to stimulate the national economy is evident. By stimulating the national economy, the domestic demand of the population can be met, and the need for imported products to meet this demand will decrease. This, in turn, leads to lower prices, higher living standards, higher life expectancy, higher employment rates, and development.

We also look at many products as finished products, but this is wrong. We should treat everything as raw material as possible. What does this help? The fact that we look at everything as a raw material leads us to create new jobs and increase the level of employment of the population. For example: We have gold and sell it to the foreign market. If we sell it not only in the bulk state, but also by processing it, making a new product from it, a lot of people will be employed in this processing process.

Summary. We should consider the products we buy from other countries not as finished products, but as raw materials. For example, we imported bananas from abroad. This process can also be turned into a process that serves to increase

the level of employment. That is, we can prepare a new product other than bananas and export it to another country. This is also a process. And all this can be one of the solutions to such a difficult problem as a migrant abroad among the people of Uzbekistan. Before, it was very difficult for migrants to be under the protection of the law. This is not the case now, a lot of work has been done to protect the rights of migrants in our country. Currently, the rights of a migrant who has left abroad legally are protected, he is under the protection of the state, he works legally, and there are no various deceptions. Therefore, it is defined that migrants go abroad legally, with a contract with the state.

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